

SHORT NOTES

An Equation Linking the Potential of the Stern-Mukherjee Layer with the Electrokinetic Potential ζ

B. N. Ghosh

While the ζ -potential is regarded as the difference of potential between the slipping plane and the interior of the solution, the potential of the Stern-Mukherjee layer (Mukherjee, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1911, 16, 103; Stern, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1924, 30, 508) may be regarded as that between the capillary surface and the slipping plane and should be denoted by $(\psi_0 - \zeta)$ where ψ_0 is the Nernst or surface potential.

For glass, which behaves as a reversible hydrogen electrode, variation of ψ_0 with the concentration C of H^+ ions in solution can be expressed by the equation

$$\psi_0 = \frac{kT}{e} \ln \frac{C_0}{C} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where C_0 is a constant and k , T , and e have their usual significance.

Similarly, by applying the Maxwell-Boltzmann law of distribution, one can write

$$C_s = C \exp. (e\zeta/kT)$$

or
$$\zeta = \frac{kT}{e} \ln \frac{C_s}{C} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where C_s represents the concentration of H^+ ions at the slipping plane.

Let us denote $(\psi_0 - \zeta)/\zeta$ by p . It then follows that,

$$p = \frac{\psi_0 - \zeta}{\zeta} = (\ln \frac{C_0}{C} - \ln \frac{C_s}{C}) / \ln \frac{C_s}{C} = \ln \frac{C_0}{C_s} / \ln \frac{C_s}{C}$$

or
$$\ln \frac{C_0}{C_s} = p \ln \frac{C_s}{C} = \ln \frac{C_s^p}{C^p}$$

or
$$C_s = (C_0 C^p)^{1/(p+1)} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Substituting the above value of C_s in equation (2) and putting $p=0.8$, we get

$$\zeta = 0.058 \log \left(\frac{C_0}{C} \right)^{1/(1+p)} = 0.032 \log C_0 - 0.032 \log C \quad (4)$$

Rutgers and de Smet (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1945, **51**, 758) have observed that the ζ -potential of Jena glass (16111) capillary wall varies linearly with $-\log C$; where C represents the concentration of the H^+ ions in solution in contact with the glass surface and the slope of the line is 0.032 and not 0.058. They have offered an interpretation different from that given above. They also have assumed that the surface potential ϵ (same as ψ_0 in equation 1) varies according to the equation

$$\epsilon = \frac{RT}{F_n} \ln \frac{C}{C_0}$$

It has been further assumed by them that (a) at C_0 the H^+ ion concentration at the glass wall is not constant, but that it varies with its concentration C in the solution; (b) according to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm $C_0 = \propto C^{0.45}$. Finally they have arrived at the equation

$$\epsilon = 0.032 \log C - \epsilon' \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where ϵ is a constant.

It may be pointed out that according to equation (5), it is the surface potential ϵ , and not ζ , which varies linearly with $0.032 \log$. What has actually been observed is that ζ varies linearly with $-\log C$.

The line of argument, which has been followed by the present author in deriving equation (4), does not involve the assumptions (a) and (b) and at the same time leads to an expression connecting ζ directly with $-\log C$ and p , which has been given a physical significance.

It may be mentioned that by giving suitable values to C_0 and p in equation (4), the results, obtained by Rutgers and de Smet (*loc. cit.*) using other univalent cations between the concentration range of 2×10^2 and $1 \times 10^4 \mu$ equivalents/litre, can also be accounted for fairly satisfactorily.